

Performance of Political Parties in General Elections to Five States' Legislative Assemblies: An Analytical Study

Dr. K. Lakshman

Assistant Professor

Department of Public Administration

Nizam College (Autonomous)

A Constituent College of Osmania University

Hyderabad, Telangana, India -500001

Abstract: -Election Commission of India has conducted general Assembly elections for five States i.e., Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Punjab, Manipur and Goa. These Legislative Assembly Elections were held in the five different States on different dates. The Election Commission of India has announced these Assembly Election Result for these States- Uttar Pradesh, Goa, Punjab, Uttarakhand and Manipur through their official website. Counting for the Assembly Elections and Results have been done on 10th February, 2022. In order to get the detailed information regarding the Assembly Election Results 2022, and Performance of various political parties in the recent elections have been discussed in this paper.

Keywords:- Elections, Political Parties, Election Results.

I. INTRODUCTION

Election Commission of India has announced to conduct Assembly elections for five States i.e., Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Punjab, Manipur and Goa. Elections to Uttar Pradesh Assembly have been held in seven phases, beginning on February 10th 2022, second phase on February 14th, third phase on February 20th, Fourth phase on February 23rd, Fifth phase on February 27th, sixth phase on March-3rd and last (seventh) phase on March 7th, while Manipur has

two-phase elections on 27th February and 3rd March 2022, in Punjab, Uttarakhand and Goa have single phase election on 14th February, 2022. The counting of votes of all the five states and results have been done on 10th March, 2022.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To describe the status of political parties in recent general assembly elections in five states;
- To analyse and comparison of election results in 2017 and 2022 elections.
- To find-out the increase or decrease of won seats and percentage of votes of political parties.

III. METHODOLOGY

For this study, we collected the data through secondary data, from official documents and websites of the Election Commission of India, and various Newspapers of Local and National levels. The study has covered the data and put the limitations for mobilizations elections results and required data and required Information.

The Chief Election Commission of India has announced that all election of five states have been conducted in seven phases, the details given below;

Elections held on	Uttara Pradesh	Uttara Khand	Manipur	Panjab	Goa
Phase-1	Febryary-10th	--	--	--	--
Phase-2	February- 14th	February- 14th	--	February- 14th	February- 14th
Phase-3	February -20th	--	--	--	--
Phase-4	February -23rd	--	--	--	--
Phase-5	February-27th	--	February-27th	--	--
Phase-6	March-3rd	--	March -3rd	--	--
Phase-7	March-7th	--	--	--	--
Counting of Votes	March 10th	March 10th	March 10th	March 10th	March 10th

Table 1: Polling/Election held in five States - Phase wise details

Source: Election Commission of India.

IV. POLLING DURING COVID PERIOD –ELECTION COMMISSION’S GUIDE LINES

- The polling time has increased by one hour.
 - The air time in Doordarshan for political parties have been doubled.
 - Political parties and candidates are advised to conduct their campaigns virtual and digital modes as much as possible instead of physical mode.
 - No roadshow, bike rally, padyatra, procession will be allowed till January 15.
 - No physical rally will be allowed till January 15. No victory celebration will be allowed.
 - *Nukkad* sabha and street meets are also banned.
 - Only two people can accompany the candidate to collect winning certificate.
 - Political parties should provide mask and sanitiser to people attending rally, if they are allowed.
 - Only five people allowed to take part in door-to-door campaigns.
- **Election Expenditure:** The election expenditure per candidate has been increased to Rs. 28 lakhs for Manipur and Goa, and Rs. 40 lakhs for the remaining three States. The CEC has encouraged people to use **eVigil app** to report any abuse of election machinery like violation of model code of conduct.
 - **Candidates with criminal records:** Optional facility of online nomination given to candidates. The CEC says that We would like candidates to use this so that physical contact is reduced. On candidates with criminal cases, the political party should explain why the person was selected despite criminal records. The candidate should advertise their criminal record in newspapers.
 - **Postal ballots for senior citizens:** Maximum number of electors per polling station reduced from 1,500 to 1,250 due to pandemic situation. Some polling stations are exclusively managed by women and persons with disabilities. All stations will be made disabled-friendly. Volunteers are available to help them. A polling team with polling officials will go to the home of senior citizen electors and they can cast their vote by postal ballot. The process has been video graphed.

V. ELECTION WITH COVID PROTOCOL

According to Chief Election Commissioner “a total of 690 Assembly constituencies in Goa, Manipur, Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand and Punjab were polled this time”. For the past two years, the impact of COVID-19 has made conduct of elections difficult. It is our duty to see how to conduct elections safely. The EC has put in place new protocols. He narrates various discussions the Commission had with various stakeholders including political parties, district magistrates etc.

VI. ASSEMBLY ELECTION RESULTS-2022

The Election Commission of India had held the Legislative Assembly Elections in the five different States on different dates. The Election Commission has announced the Assembly Election Result for the States: Uttar Pradesh, Goa, Punjab, Uttarakhand and Manipur through their official website. Counting for the Assembly Election Results have been done on 10th February 2022 and the Assembly Election Results also announced on the same date.

There are 403 Assembly Constituencies in Uttar Pradesh, 117 in Punjab, 40 in Goa, 60 in Manipur, and 70 in Uttarakhand. A majority of constituencies must be won by a single political party or alliance parties to form a State government; it must win more than 50% of seats. As part of the Assembly Elections in the various constituencies and States, candidates of diverse political parties have been elected, including the Bharatiya Janata Party, India National Congress, and Samajwadi Party.

BJP bags highest vote share in a UP election since 1977. AAP wins highest seats in Punjab since 1997. Both Bharatiya Janata Party and Aam Admi Party have not just swept the election in Uttar Pradesh and Punjab respectively, they have broken records of decades. BJP has become the only party after 1977 to breach the 40% vote share mark in Uttar Pradesh assembly elections. In Punjab, it is after 1997 that any party has touched the 93 seat won registered by the Shiromani Akali Dal.

The Election Commission data showed Bharatiya Janata Party bagging a 41.3 % vote share. In 1977, the Janata party had touched a 47.8% vote share high in Uttara Pradesh. Every political party that has formed government in Uttara Pradesh since then- from the Congress to Bharatiya Janata Party, Samajwadi Party and Bahujan Samaj Party- have either been under or hovering at the 39-40% vote share mark when forming government.

In 2022, the BJP has bagged lesser seats than in 2017 but moved up its vote share from 39.6% to near 42%- indicating both the deepening and widening of its voter base in the state. Alongside, the Samajwadi Party has made an impressive improvement in its vote share at 32%- up from 21.8% in 2017 polls and even higher than the 29% it touched in 2012 when it formed government. This, however, was not enough to beat the Bharatiya Janata Party juggernaut.

The third major party in the fray- Bahujan Samaj Party has hit its lowest point since 1996 with a vote share of no more than 12.7%. It was at 22.23% in the last assembly election. Bahujan Samaj Party, in fact, has seen its vote share also cut down significantly in adjacent Uttarakhand - to the lowest ever at 4.8%. The Congress is decimated registering a 2.3% vote – big slide down from even its last poor showing of 6.2% vote share in 2017.

Bharatiya Janata Party held on to or somewhat improved upon its 2017 vote share in four of the five states UttaraKhand being the exception, while Congress saw sharp declines in its shares everywhere except the hill state.

Among the major regional players, SP improved its vote share in Uttara Pradesh by more than 10 percentage points while the BSP dropped nearly as much in the state. AAP nearly doubled its share in Panjab, enabling it to sweep the state. In Manipur, Congress has hit its lowest vote share ever at 16.5%- from its 35% high in 2017. In Goa, BJP bagged 33% and 20 seats up from 32.5% share and 13 seats in 2017.

Five states -Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Punjab, Manipur and Goa - went go to the polls in February-March 2022. Uttar Pradesh has 403 assembly seats, Uttarakhand 80, Punjab 117, Manipur 60 and Goa 40. The assembly elections result for the five states have been declared on 10th March 2022. Of the five states that went to the polls, four

are being ruled by the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP). Punjab is ruled by the Congress. Both Uttar Pradesh and Punjab are seeing multi-cornered assembly polls.

A. Uttar Pradesh – Assembly Elections

In Uttar Pradesh, the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) has faced challenges from the Samajwadi Party (SP), the Bahujan Samaj Party (BSP) and the Congress. The Aam Aadmi Party (AAP) is looked in to play a role in Uttar Pradesh with a possible tie-up with the SP, which in turn has announced alliances with the Rashtriya Lok Dal (RLD) and the Suheldev Bharatiya Samaj Party (SBSP). While BJP made alliance with Apna Dal (Senelal) and NISHAD party. Congress and BSP are contested separately.

Party	Seats	Alliance	Alliance Total
Bharatiya Janata Party	255	NDA	273
Apna Dal (Senelal)	12		
NISHAD Party	06		
Samajwadi Party	111	SP+	125
Rashtriya Lok Dal	08		
Suheldev Bharatiya Samaj Party	06		
Indian National Congress	02	UPA	2
Janasatta Dal (Loktantrik)	02	None	2
Bhahujan Samajwadi Party	01		1
Total seats	403		

Table 2: Seats won by political parties in Uttara Pradesh in 2022

Source: Election Commission of India

The above data shows that the performance of political parties in general elections for Uttara Pradesh state assemblies held in the month of February and March 2022. In this election BJP won the with its alliance partners Apna dal (Senelal) and NISHAD party, total 273 of 403 total

assembly seats. While Samajwadi Party has won 125 with its alliance parties RLD and Suheldev Bharatiya Samaj Party. Indian National Congress just won in two seats, Janasatta Dal won in two seats and BSP won in only seat.

Name of The Political Party	Elections in 2017		Elections in 2022		Seats -increased / decreased (+ / -)	% of votes increased/ decreased (+ / -)
	No. of Seats	Percentage of Votes	No. of Seats	Percentage of Votes		
BJP+	322	40.65%	273	44%	-49	+3%
SP+	52	23.6%	125	37%	+73	13%
BSP	19	22.23%	01	3%	-18	-9%
INC	07	6.25%	02	2%	-5	-4%
others	03	7.27%	02	4%	-1	-3%
Total	403	100%	403	--	--	--

Table 3: Performance of Political Parties in Uttara Pradesh- Assembly Elections 2017-2022

Source: Election Commission of India

In 2022, the BJP has bagged lesser seats than in 2017 but moved up its vote share from 39.7% to near 42%- indicating both the deepening and widening of its voter base in the state.

Alongside, the Samajwadi party has made an impressive improvement in its vote share at 32%- up from 21.8% in 2017 polls and even higher than the 29% it touched in 2012 when it formed government.

In Uttara Pradesh, BJP gained nearly two percentage votes, from 39.7% in 2017 to 41.6% this time, which meant that even the jump from 21.8% to 32% in SP's vote share

was not enough to bridge the huge gap. BSP fell from 22.2% to 12.7% and Congress from 6.3% to a mere 2.4%, below even RLD's 3% share.

This, however, was not enough to beat the BJP juggernaut. The third major party in the fray- Bahujan Samaj Party has hit its lowest point since 1996 with a vote share of no more than 12.7%. It was at 22.23% in the last assembly election.

BSP, in fact, has seen its vote share also cut down significantly in adjacent Uttarakhand - to the lowest ever at 4.8%. The Congress is decimated registering a 2.3% vote –

big slide down from even its last poor showing of 6.2% vote share in 2017.

B. Uttarakhand- Assembly Elections

In Uttarakhand, the electoral contest seems direct between the BJP and the Congress, which hopes to return to power by pocketing anti-incumbency votes. The AAP is also looking to make its debut in the Uttarakhand Assembly next year.

The Congress, in fact, has seen its vote share plummet from 40% in 2017 polls to 23% in this round. In Uttarakhand, the Bharatiya Janata Party has retained its vote share at 44%- though lower than the 46.5% it earned in 2017. The Congress has moved up from 33.5% to 38% and also improved its overall tally.

Name of The Political Party	Elections in 2017		Elections in 2022		Seats -increased / decreased (+ / -)	% of votes increased/ decreased (+ / -)
	No. of Seats	Percentage of Votes	No. of Seats	Percentage of Votes		
BJP	57	46.6%	47	44%	-10	-2%
INC	11	33.6%	19	38%	+10	+4%
AAP	00	0%	00	3%	0	+3%
others	02	18.7%	04	15%	+2	-4%
Total	60	100%	60	100%	--	--

Table 4: Performance of Political Parties in Uttarakhand - Assembly Elections 2017 and 2022

Source: Election Commission of India

In Uttarakhand, Congress improved from 33.5% to 37.9%, but was still well short of BJP's 44.3%, which represented a decline from 46.5% in 2017. BSP, in fact, has seen its vote share also cut down significantly in adjacent Uttarakhand - to the lowest ever at 4.8%. The Congress is decimated registering a 2.3% vote – big slide down from even its last poor showing of 6.2% vote share in 2017.

In Uttarakhand, the BJP has retained its vote share at 44%- though lower than the 46.5% it earned in 2017. The Congress has moved up from 33.5% to 38% and also improved its overall tally. Bahujan Samaj Party, in fact, has

seen its vote share also cut down significantly in adjacent Uttarakhand - to the lowest ever at 4.8%. The Congress is decimated registering a 2.3% vote – big slide down from even its last poor showing of 6.2% vote share in 2017.

C. Punjab- Assembly Elections

In Punjab, the Congress is fighting on multiple fronts - both within and outside the party - to retain power. Former Punjab Chief Minister Captain Amarinder Singh has floated his own outfit and is likely to tie up with the BJP. The Shiromani Akali Dal (SAD) has allied with the BSP, for the first time since the 1996 Punjab election.

Name of The Political Party	Elections in 2017		Elections in 2022		Seats -increased / decreased (+ / -)	% of votes increased/decreased (+ / -)
	No. of Seats	Percentage of Votes	No. of Seats	Percentage of Votes		
INC	77	38%	18	23%	-59	-15%
BJP	03	5.1%	02	08%	-1	+3%
AAP	20	23.6%	92	42%	+72	+18%
SAD	15	25.5%	04	20%	-11	-5%
INP	--	--	00	1%	--	0%
others	02	7%	01	7%	--	--

Table 5: Performance of Political Parties in Panjab -Assembly Elections 2017 and 2022

Source: Election Commission of India

In Punjab, AAP went from 23.7% in 2017 to 42%, the highest it's got in the state, while Congress fell from 38.5% to 23% and Akali Dal from 25.2% to 18.4%. The trend is mirrored in Punjab where the Congress vote share is heavily down from 38.6% in 2017 to 22.96% in 2022. The Aam Aadmi Party is a true giant killer upping its vote share from 14.8% and 20 seats in 2017 to 92 seats and a solid 42% vote share. More interestingly, no party has won as many seats in the last four assembly elections as AAP. SAD had notched a 93 seats in the 1997 elections. The winning party in Punjab has stayed under 70 since then except for the Congress clocking a 77 seat victory in the last assembly elections. The

Congress, in fact, has seen its vote share plummet from 40% in 2017 polls to 23% in this round.

D. Manipur- Assembly Elections

In Manipur, BJP is leading a coalition government though the Congress had emerged as the single-largest party in the 2017 assembly polls. The National People's Party (PPP) that rules Meghalaya is looking to expand in Manipur. It has said it would field 40-45 candidates in the assembly polls. The Congress and the Left Front are likely to continue their alliance in Manipur despite failure in the West Bengal Assembly election 2021.

Name of The Political Party	Elections in 2017		Elections in 2022		Seats -increased / decreased (+ / -)	% of votes increased/ decreased (+ / -)
	No. of Seats	Percentage of Votes	No. of Seats	Percentage of Votes		
INC	28	35.2%	05	17%	-23	-18%
BJP	21	36.4%	32	38%	+11	+1%
Other	11	28.4%	23	45%	+12	+17%

Table 6: Performance of Political Parties in Manipur -Assembly Elections 2017 and 2022

Source: Election Commission of India

In Manipur, BJP slightly hiked its share from 36.3% to 37.7% while Congress plunged from 35.1% to 16.6%, below even NPP's 17.1%. In Manipur, Congress has hit its lowest vote share ever at 16.5% - from its 35% high in 2017. In Manipur, Congress has hit its lowest vote share ever at 16.5% - from its 35% high in 2017.

E. Goa- Assembly Elections

In Goa, too, the BJP formed the government in 2017 despite coming behind the Congress in the assembly polls. But since then, the Congress has suffered massive defections to the BJP, which now enjoys a majority in the assembly. The Trinamool Congress (TMC) and the AAP are looking at the Goa Assembly election as an opportunity to expand their bases. This makes the Goa election a multi-cornered contest.

Name of The Political Party	Elections in 2017		Name of The Political Party	Elections in 2022		Seats -increased / decreased (+ / -)	% of votes increased/ decreased (+ / -)
	No. of Seats	Percentage of Votes		No. of Seats	Percentage of Votes		
BJP	13	32%	BJP	20	34%	+7	+2%
INC	20	38%	INC+	12	26%	-8	-12%
TMC	03	10%	TMC+	02	12%	-1	+12%
APP	00	63%	APP	02	07%	+2	+1%
Other	--	13.3%	Other	04	21%	--	+8%
Total	40	100%	--	40	100%	--	--

Table 7: Performance of Political Parties in Goa -Assembly Elections 2017 and 2022

Source: Election Commission of India

In Goa, BJP marginally raised its share from 32.5% to 33.3%, but with Congress declining sharply from 28.4% to 23.5%, that proved just about enough. In Goa, BJP bagged 33% and 20 seats up from 32.5% share and 13 seats in 2017.

VII. CONCLUSION

Bharatiya Janata Party held on to or somewhat improved upon its 2017 vote share in four of the five states UttaraKhand being the exception — while Congress saw sharp declines in its shares everywhere except the hill state. Among the major regional players, SP improved its vote share in Uttara Pradesh by more than 10 percentage points while the BSP dropped nearly as much in the state. AAP nearly doubled its share in Panjab, enabling it to sweep the state. The five assembly elections cover 102 Lok Sabha constituencies and the assembly elections taking place little over two years to the next parliamentary polls in 2024.

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